

14. QOSIMOVA M. TO DEVELOP STUDENTS'SKILLS OF NATURE CONSERVATION AND RESPECT FOR HUMAN LABOR BY TEACHING THEM TO SOLVE ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 2.
15. Qosimov F. M., Qosimova M. M. Ikki (yoki bir necha) sonni ularning yigindisi va ayirmasiga kora topishga doir masalalar //Scientific progress. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 1138-1145.
16. Muxammedovich Q. F., Muxammedovna Q. M. Technology of work on comparison tasks //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2019. – Т. 2019.
17. Kasimov F., Kasimova M., Uktamova D. Specific principles for constructing a system of educational tasks //Bridge to science: research works. – 2019. – С. 211.
18. Qosimov F. M., Qosimova M. M. MATEMATIKADAN IJODIY O 'QUV TOPSHIRIQLARINING METODIK XUSUSIYATLARI //BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 206-211.
19. Qosimov M. F., Kasimov F. F. Methods of teaching to solve non-standard problems //Middle European Scientific Bulletin. – 2021. – Т. 11.
20. Касимов Ф. М., Касимова М. М., Хакимова М. Х. Специфические принципы построения системы учебных задач //Психология и педагогика: методика и проблемы практического применения. – 2016. – №. 50-2. – С. 58-62.

2-SINF MATEMATIKA DARSLIGIDA BERILGAN MUSTAQIL TOPSHIRIQLARNING TA'LIMIY VA TARBIYAVIY AHAMIYATI

Aziza Avaz qizi Rahmonova

BuxDPI magistri

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmasi, ijodiy qobiliyat, o'quv jarayonida mustaqil topshiriqlarni bajarish orqali o'quvchilarda ijodiy fikrlash qobiliyatini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari haqidagi so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: mustaqil fikrlash, mustaqil topshiriq, mustaqil ishlash ko'nikmasi, ijodiy qobiliyat, hayotiy ko'nikmalar

So'nggi yillarda mamlakatda ta'lim-tarbiya tizimining sifati va samaradorligini oshirish, bog'cha tarbiyalanuvchilari, o'quvchi va talaba yoshlarda zamonaviy bilim va ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish, ta'lim tizimlari hamda ilm-fan sohasi o'rtasida yaqin hamkorlik va integratsiyani, ta'limning uzviyligi va uzluksizligini ta'minlash borasida tizimli ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Shu bilan birga, milliy ta'lim-tarbiya tizimining amaldagi holati uni zamon talablari asosida modernizatsiya qilish, yoshlarni yuksak bilim-ma'rifat egalari, jismoniy va ma'naviy sog'lom insonlar etib tarbiyalash, ta'lim muassasalarining rahbar va pedagog xodimlari nufuzini oshirish, ularning samarali faoliyat yuritishi uchun zarur shart-sharoitlar yaratish bo'yicha izchil choratadbirlarni amalga oshirishni talab etmoqda. Shubhasiz, inson tarbiyasi va uning ijodiy qobiliyatlari Milliy dasturni amalga oshirishda asosiy o'rin egallaydi. Inson omili mazmuni milliy dasturi ko'plab zarur vazifalarni hal qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Milliy dastur asosida tashkil topgan Matematika darsligi ham juda ko'p g'oyaviy yangiliklarni uchratish mumkin. Bundan tashqari 2-sinf darsliklarini tahlili qiladigan bo'lsak, ushbu darslikda ko'plab ta'limiy yangiliklarni kuzatishimiz mumkin. Matematika darsligida hozirgi kunda o'quvchilarning dunyo qarashinin rivojlantirish, mustaqil fikrlash, erkin so'zlash, hayotiy realliklarga asoslangan desak adashmagan bo'lamiz, chunki har bir topshiriqlar rang- baranglikni, hayotiy tasvirga oid topshiriqlarni, mantiqiy topshiriqlarni bundan tashqari mustaqil topshiriqlarni ham kuzatishimiz mumkin. Darslikdagi mustaqil topshiriqlarni tahlil qiladigan bo'lsak, bu turdagi topshiriqlar aqlini charxlaydi, diqqatini rivojlantiradi, ko'zlangan maqsadga erishish uchun qat'iyat va irodani tarbiyalaydi, algoritmik tarzda tartib- intizomlilikka o'rgatadi va eng muhimi mulohaza yuritishga chorlaydi hamda tafakkurni kengaytiradi. 2- sinf Matematika darsliklardagi mustaqil topshiriqlarning sonini aniqlash maqsadida ularni tahlil qilindi.

Bularni quyidagicha jadval asosida ko'rish mumkin.

MAVZUVIY REJALASHTIRISH

№	Bo'lim va boblar nomi	Soatlar taqsimoti			
		Jami	Nazariy	Amaliy topshiriq va N.I.	Mustaqil topshiriqlar
	1-sinfda o'tilgan materiallarni takrorlash va umumlashtirish	10		10	
1	Yuz ichida sonlarni qo'shish	20	10	10	14
2	Yuz ichida sonlarni ayirish	20	10	10	7
3	Geometrik shakllar	15	5	10	6
4	Sonlarni ko'paytirish	20	10	10	8
5	Sonlarni bo'lish	30	10	20	10
6	Sonli ifodalar. Tenglamalar.	15	5	10	11
7	Ulushlar	15	5	10	7
8	Ma'lumotlar bilan ishlash. Vaqt	15	5	10	6
	Takrorlash	10		10	
	Jami:	170	60	110	69

Bu jadval orqali ko'rish mumkinki, darslikdagi mustaqil topshiriqlarning umumiy soni 69 ta tashkil qilgan. Bunday topshiriqlarning afzalligi shundan iboratki, o'quvchilarni topshiriqlikka, fikrlashga, izlanishga, dunyoqarashini kengayishiga asos bo'ladi. Shu tariqa o'quvchilar kelajakda o'z imkoniyatlarini ko'rsata bilishga qiynalishmaydi. Matematika darsligidagi mustaqil ishlaridan namunalar keltirib asoslab chiqsak

E'tibor beramiz :

Mashinaning qaysi detali noodatiy? (Uning g'ildiraklari)

G'ildiraklarning vazifasi nima? (Yo'lda yurish)

U vazifasini bajarish uchun qanday harakatlanadi? (Tez harakatlanadi)

Kvadrat shaklidagi g'ildiraklar ham aylana shaklidagi g'ildiraklar kabi harakatlanadimi? (Yo'q harakatlanadimi) degan savollar orqali o'quvchilarga savollar beriladi.. Bunday mulohazali savollar orqali o'quvchilar quyidagi tayanch kompetensiya shakllanadi, ya'ni kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni shakllantiriladi. Bu jrayonda ijodiy fikrlash, yozma va og'zaki ravon bayon etish, to'g'ri talaffuz qilish, izohlab berish hamda erkin muloqot qilishga o'rgatish zarur bo'ladi. Xususan, matematika fanining o'z ilmiy tili, o'z tushunchalari, belgi va timsollari ham mavjud bo'lib, bu tilda muloqot qilish - kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish omili sifatida qaralishi lozim bo'ladi. Bu usuldagi mustaqil topshiriqlar Geometrik munosabatlar haqida matematik va mantiqiy fikrni rivojlantirish vazifasini bajaradi. Bundan tashqari o'zlashtirilgan bilim va ko'nikmalarini amaliy masalalarni yechishda va notanish vaziyatlarda qo'llay olish kompetensiyalar biri Mulohaza yuritish (M1) shakllanadi . (M1)da matematikaga oid fikrni asoslash, isbotlash yoki o'zgaralar fikriga munosabat bildirish uchun mantiqan asosli va tushunarli dalillarni keltirishga undaydi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, bugungi kunda biz bolalarning maqsadlarini to'g'ri yo'naltirsak, kelajakda o'z qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirishi va albatta komil inson sifatida shakllanishi mumkin. Milliy o'quv dasturining asosiy vazifalari shuni e'tiborga oldiki, oldingi standartdan farqli tomoni - o'quvchi muvaffaqiyatga erishishi uchun kerak bo'lgan asosiy kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishni maqsad qilib qo'ydi. Bularga **tanqidiy fikrlash, ijodiy fikrlash, kommunikativlik (muloqotga kirishish), axborot bilan ishlash, o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish va faol fuqarolik** kabilardir. Bizga qanday avlod kerak deganda bizga ilg'or fikrlaydigan, qat'iyatli, o'z maqsadi sari harakat qiladigan, mustaqil qaror qabul qila oladigan, muammoni ijobiy yechadigan shaxslarni yetishtirish kerak.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti SH. Mirziyoyev 06.11.20, PF-6108-son
2. Umumiy o'rta ta'limning Milliy o'quv dasturi.
3. Boshlang'ich ta'lim Konsepsiyasi.
4. O'rinboyeva L., Jumayev M., Ruzikulova N. va boshq. Matematika 2-sinf darslik. – Toshkent: Respublika ta'lim markazi, 2021.
5. O'rinboyeva L., Jumayev M., Ruzikulova N. va boshq. Matematika 2-sinf. Metodik qo'llanma Toshkent: Respublika ta'lim markazi, 2021.
6. Azixodjaeva N. N. O'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshirishda pedagogik texnologiyalar. - T.: 2007.
7. Abdullayeva B.S., Saidova M.J., Dilova N.G. Ta'limda multimedia texnologiyalaridan foydalanish. Darslik. – Toshkent, 2021.
8. Abdullayeva B.S. Fanlararo aloqadorlikning metodologik-didaktik asoslari: Ped. fan. dok. diss... — Toshkent: TDPU, 2006.
9. Abdullayeva B.S., Saidova M.J., Dilova N.G. Matematika o'qitish metodikasi. Darslik. 2021.
10. Bikbayeva N.U., Sidelnikova R. Boshlang'ich sinflarda matematika o'qitish metodikasi. - T: "O'qituvchi", – 1986.
11. GE Saidova - PEDAGOGS jurnali, 2022. PIRLS–BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLAR O'QUVCHILARINING BAHOLASH DASTURIDA ISHTIROK ETISHI.
12. T Khojaoglu, SG Ergashovna - International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 2022 The Practical Importance of Using the Scientific Heritage of the Eastern Thinkers in the Education of the Young Generation
13. Г Саидова, Н Авлиёкулова - Общество и инновации, 2022 Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'quv jarayonini zamonaviy, innovatsion texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish.
14. Г Саидова, Н Авлиёкулова - Общество и инновации, 2022/4/28 Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'quv jarayonini zamonaviy, innovatsion texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish.
15. Г Саидова, А Каххорова - Общество и инновации, 2022/5/15 Xalq og'zaki ijodi orqali o'quvchilarda ma'naviy tarbiyani shakllantirish.
16. SG Ergashovna, AN Choriyevna. Use of Advanced Foreign Experiences in Increasing the Efficiency of Classroom and Out-of-Class Lessons. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 2023
17. G Saidova BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIMDA MODULLI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ILMiy-PEDAGOGIK ASOSLARI ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 2023/1/31
18. Saidova M. EDUCATE STUDENTS BY SOLVING TEXTUAL PROBLEMS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – T. 7. – №. 12.
19. Saidova M. J. Methods and Importance of Using Innovative Technologies in Learning Concenter "Decimal" at Teaching Process of Math in Primary Schools //www. auris-verlag. de. – 2017.
20. Saidova Mohinur Jonpulatovna, Ibrahimova Mohichehra Furkat Qizi. An integrated approach to the use of pedagogical technologies in primary school mathematics// Middle European Scientific Bulletin. Volume 8, January 2021, 174

INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE KINDERGARTEN

Inoyatova Dilnoza Ilhomovna

Teacher of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Zakiryayeva Malika Azizovna

Student of Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation: *This article describes the strategies which are dedicated to the modern teaching English language through interactive methods in kindergarten. In this article, there are also several instructions which help to improve the efficiency of the lesson in kindergarten.*

Key words: *interactive methods, theoretical, practical parts, communication, interaction, second language, visual aids.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье описаны стратегии, посвященные современному обучению английскому языку интерактивными методами в детском саду. В этой статье также есть несколько инструкций, которые помогут повысить эффективность урока в детском саду.*

Ключевые слова: *интерактивные методы, теоретическая, практическая части, коммуникация, взаимодействие, второй язык, наглядные пособия*

In this day and age, English language plays an integral role in all spheres, namely, education, industries, politics, media, library, business, communication around the world and others. That is why, the popularity of both teaching and learning English language as a second language is increasing at an alarming rate. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in research in English, which is considered as the language of professional communication in different fields of activity. Thus, increasing enthusiasm for learning English is one of the most decisive tasks of a teacher. In fact, it is better to start learning a foreign language from a very young age. Because young children's brains continue to develop without stopping, they have the ability to absorb new information much faster than adults whose brains are fully formed. It is appropriate to plan a lesson taking into account these peculiarities. For example, the use of games, pictures, songs and poems, cartoons is an effective way to teach foreign language to children of preschool age. (1). If we want teach English to children of preschool, it requires plays, acts, songs, in general we should make learning a language a fun for them. Generally, we used to utilize the standard teaching of foreign languages. In other words, teachers always explain the themes, speak as well as show some cards in order to being understandable the information to children, otherwise, students listen, write all of the notes from the desks or whiteboards and memorize. At the end of the lessons, teachers give some quizzes and tests which are helpful to find out what the children have learned. This is called a passive teaching method, additionally, this method is also obsolete. But there is another method which is known as an active teaching method. It consists of a wider interaction of children not only with the teacher, but also with their pairs. During the interactive lessons, children work in small groups, create projects. If teachers only pay attention to the theoretical parts, the lesson will be boring, as a result, interests of children in learning English gradually decrease. That is why, we should take into account both practical and theoretical parts in equal. There are a lot of interactive methods.

Total Physical Response (TPR)

Total or full physical response method is widely used for working with children of kindergarten and primary school ages. Besides giving speeches by teachers in the classes, children take part into the learning processes by repeating words with various emotional shades, movements or dances during using this method. This strategy is universal, because we can use it for working with all types of learners, such as kinesthetic, visuals and auditory